

PROOF OF THE POSSIBILITY FOR A PUBLIC AUDIT OF A SECRET INTERNET VOTING SYSTEM

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to prove the possibility of building a system of secret Internet voting, in which a full-fledged audit is available to all voters and their proxies. A full-fledged audit should be understood as such an audit, in which everything that may be in doubt is checked. The open block of servers was created using Raspberry Pi 3 Model B type minicomputers, which are widely known and well-established. On the basis of an open block of servers, a full-scale model of the system for conducting experimental voting was created and a detailed methodology for a full-fledged audit was developed. This methodology provides for two stages of the audit. In the first stage, voters or their proxies must be present near the server unit. In the second stage, they continue the audit remotely through a dedicated server without losing information about the security of their data. For practical acquaintance with this research, the possibility of experimental voting is given. The experiment can be conducted by anyone at any time through a link on the Internet. Thus, it is shown that not only with traditional secret voting technologies, a full-fledged audit is possible, thanks to which voters have no doubts about maintaining the secrecy of their votes and the honesty of the results. To conduct a full-fledged audit according to the described methodology, it is not require to involve highly qualified specialists, but school education, which is mandatory in many countries, is quite enough. The importance of the results is that the lack of a full-fledged audit of Internet voting systems is the main factor hindering the development of e-democracy. The lack of public auditing of Internet voting systems causes distrust in the possibility of using the Internet to conduct fair elections.

Keywords: secret Internet voting, open server block, audit of Internet voting.

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1. Introduction

Internet technologies are steadily penetrating and deepening into the processes of our activity. However, in the elections of government representatives, where the fate of many citizens and entire states is decided, the introduction of new technologies is problematic. In countries with developed democracies, due to the availability of audit, there is no electoral fraud, and they do not want to lose this achievement when switching to new technologies. The recommendations of the Council of the EU on the standards of electronic voting, adopted on June 14, 2017, point 39 states: «The e-voting system shall be auditable. The audit system shall be open and comprehensive, and actively report on potential issues and threats». Whatever the software and hardware of electronic voting, but if for voters they represent a «black box», then it is not possible to eliminate suspicions of fraud. In fact, there is no other way to ensure the trust of voters than giving them the opportunity to conduct a full-fledged audit. A full-fledged audit should be understood as such an audit, in which everything that may be in doubt is checked. The purpose of the study is to prove the possibility of building a system of secret Internet voting, in which a full-fledged audit is available to all voters and their proxies.

2. Materials and methods

In [1], a protest is expressed about the on-line election of representatives of power due to the fact that the audit, which is usually carried out by the voters themselves, becomes impracticable. It is indicated that in this case, specialists will be able to easily change the voting results. In the work on improving Internet voting systems, two areas of research can be distinguished. The first one is the development of the Estonian system, which does not use Blockchain technology, and the second one is the systems based on Blockchain technology. In [2], attacks on the Estonian system were analyzed, where it was revealed that an attacker can re-vote using fake software, and a more secure voting protocol was proposed. In [3], in order to strengthen the confidence of voters, it is proposed to conduct cyber risk checks by knowledgeable users. However, the issues of auditing hardware and software by the voters themselves, for whom the Estonian system is a «black box», are not touched upon. To ensure trust in voting systems, the use of Blockchain technology has been proposed and patented [4]. Research in this direction is ongoing, which is reflected in the works [5–8], where proposals are made to improve security and anonymity for voters, as well as to counteract dishonesty on the part of candidates. However, it is difficult to imagine a widely available audit in systems using Blockchain technology, since this technology is understandable only to a limited circle of specialists. Thus, there is a gap in research on Internet voting in terms of ensuring widely accessible audit by voters. Note that such an audit is required in accordance with paragraph 39 of the recommendations of the EU Council on e-voting standards [9]. This allows to assert that the proof of the possibility of building an Internet voting system, in which a full-fledged audit is available to all voters, is appropriate.

To achieve this goal, it was necessary to solve the following tasks:

- identify blocks and procedures in the voting system that may cause distrust of voters;
- choose the principles of building a system of secret Internet voting, providing the possibility of conducting an audit by voters;
- develop a methodology for a full- fledged audit of the voting system;
- perform full-scale modeling of the secret Internet voting system with an audit according to the developed methodology.

To solve the tasks set, the theory of computer networks and cryptography were used. Also, the method of research was full-scale modeling of electronic voting systems with audit tools. An important role in the comparative testing of various versions of models and the selection of the most successful technical solutions was taken by students and teachers of three higher educational institutions in Kyiv. The Kyiv National University of Construction and Architecture assumed the leading role. Students and teachers of the National Aviation University and the National Technical University of Ukraine «Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute» took an active part in the research, as well as employees of the Research Institute of Automated Systems in Construction, which provided technical support for research tools and access to the Internet. The participants in the study gave their consent to the use of their photographs in the article.

3. Research results

3. 1. Identification of blocks and procedures that may cause distrust of voters

Voters' fears regarding the violation of their legal rights can be associated only with the following two cases:

- disclosure of the secret of the voice;
- falsification of vote counting.

The transmission of information during Internet voting is carried out through public channels, where all blocks participating in the transmission process should be distrusted. In the absence of means of protecting communication channels, attackers can both reveal votes and spoof data by organizing an attack by an intermediary (MITM – Man in the middle). Distrust may be manifested towards the server block, which receives and counts the votes of voters, since there is a threat of malicious interference by service personnel in the operation of this block. Also, the procedure for displaying the results of the vote count can cause distrust. In addition to the listed objects, the voter register can cause distrust, where extra people can be entered, instead of whom violators will vote.

As pointed out in [10], this is easily identified by publishing data on the number of voters for each street within a polling station, for each house within a street, and for each apartment within a house. Then the voters themselves will find extra residents in their apartments, extra apartments in their houses and extra houses on their streets without the use of technical means. With open publication of the results for each polling station, it is not possible to falsify the total voting results, since any inaccuracy is easily detected. Thus, a complete list of blocks and procedures that may cause distrust of voters during Internet voting has been determined.

3. 2. Choice of principles for constructing a voting system with the possibility of conducting an audit by the voters themselves

In order to ensure that a full-fledged audit can be carried out by the voters themselves, all technical solutions of the voting system must be easy to understand. The hardware and software that receives and records votes must be open to inspections. It is necessary to provide an opportunity for citizens to involve their trusted specialists for inspections. An important role for demonstrating the flawless operation of the voting server belongs to the audit server, which detects and documents interference in the operation of the voting server. The device connection diagram suitable for the required audit of the Internet voting system from [10] is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the Internet voting system

In this scheme, the voting and audit servers are located in the same network, which ensures the reliability and speed of the audit procedures. Voters should make sure that their communication sessions with the voting server are protected from leakage and distortion of information. For this purpose, it is possible to use the end-to-end encryption technology described in [11]. The small amount of information sent by the voter to the voting server (about 60 bytes) allows the use of the Vernam cipher. This cipher is extremely simple to understand and for software implementation and its absolute security was mathematically proven in [12]. In **Table 1** describes the conditions that must be met for the absolute protection of transmitted data.

Table 1
Conditions for ensuring absolute data protection during transmission

Condition	Condition fulfillment
Getting random bit sequences (not pseudo-random)	The method of obtaining random bits described in [13] is used, which is applicable on any computer
Each random sequence can be used once	For each communication session, their random bit sequences are generated independently of each other
To transmit random bit sequences, an absolutely secure communication channel should be used	The exchange of random bit sequences (keys) occurs according to the Diffie-Hellman algorithm [14] with such parameters for which there is no possibility of data disclosure under modern conditions

Since the key exchange is carried out according to the Diffie-Hellman algorithm, when connecting the voter to the server, it is necessary to make sure that there is no man-in-the-middle attack. On the example of the server of the experimental polling station, let's show the actions

of the voter to detect such an attack. Through an Internet access device, the voter downloads a web page from the link <http://91.198.50.130:29900/VD999900.html>, the view of which is shown in **Fig. 2**. The top row of buttons is needed by the voter, both for voting and for auditing. The rest of the buttons are needed to switch the experiment modes, which can happen automatically at the set time points during real voting.

Polling Station No. 999900

for experimental voting

Voting actions (only valid within the electoral process)

Enter the voting code
Voting
Obtaining voting results
Server Audit

Election process periods

Period	Beginning of the period	Duration of the period
Voting code entry	Once a key is pressed	6 minutes (or Once "Begin the vote" key is pressed)
Voting	After voting code is entered	6 minutes (or Once "Complete voting" key is pressed)
Obtaining voting results	After the voting is complete	Until the end of experiment

Experimental Election Control Options

Start voting code entry
Begin the vote
Complete voting
Finish the experiment

Fig. 2. View of the web page of the polling station

To perform an audit, the voter needs to press the «Server Audit» button. At the same time, the web page of the audit server will open in a new window, the view of which is shown in **Fig. 3**.

Server Audit On Polling Station No.999900

List of connection codes
List of main processes
OS command
Audit protocol

Admin file audit

List of files
File contents

Advice and clarification

Information to the voter

Fig. 3. View of the audit server web page

The voter can conduct a dialogue with the vote counting server in one window, and control the operation of this server in the other. When a voter contacts the server, code words are exchanged according to the Diffie-Hellman algorithm to create a secure connection key. Each such connection is assigned a code, which is the first four bytes of the code word sent to the voter by the server. This code (Connection code) is shown in **Fig. 4** in the dialogue window of the voter with the server.

In order to make sure that there is no man-in-the-middle attack, it is enough for the voter in the audit window, by pressing the «List of connection codes» key, to compare the received code (in this example: D2F24813) for a match with what is indicated in the log line after the date and time of connection establishment with the server. A fragment of the connection log is shown in **Fig. 5**.

If the code in both windows matches, the voter makes sure that his/her confidential data is actually transferred to the regular server and cannot be decrypted during transmission. Since the task of encrypting and counting votes is not difficult, both JavaScript programming modules (client

and server) are easily checked for correctness. The voter can compare the texts used and published on the site after checking the program, which takes several minutes using standard tools. Next, it is necessary to make sure that the processing of data by the voting server was not subjected to any outside interference. Thanks to the block of servers installation open for inspection, shown in Fig. 6, and the choice of well-known hardware and software, these suspicions are easily eliminated.

Fig. 4. Selector dialog box with connection code

```
cat /home/admin/JOURNAL.TXT  
  
03.02.2022 00:13:04 105A5A24  
  
03.02.2022 00:16:35 D2F24813
```

Fig. 5. A fragment of the voter's connection log with the server in the audit window

Fig. 6. Appearance of an open block of servers

In [15], it is proposed to use a well-known minicomputer such as Raspberry Pi 3 Model B as the hardware for the voting server. This computer has high reliability, low cost, low power consumption, and is suitable for open mounting. It has a characteristic appearance that allows to visually identify all its constituent elements. In terms of performance, it is quite suitable for a vote counting server on the scale of a polling station. OpenBSD of the minimum configuration was chosen as the operating system. This choice is due to the high data protection requirements underlying the development of this system, as well as its complete openness for any checks. In **Table 2**

summarizes all possible types of suspicions regarding data processing by the server and ways to eliminate them.

Table 2

Elimination of suspicions in violation of the normal operation of the server

Possible suspicion	Eliminate suspicion
Replacement of the server	Openness of the server for inspection by voters and their proxies. In case of claims, the replacement of the dubious server is allowed. Voters are given the right to connect their console to the server to execute equipment check commands. Once OpenBSD is loaded, it is not possible to stealthily change the server
Changing the operating system (OS)	Voters are given the right to participate in downloading the operating system according to an open instruction. After that, it is possible to check the OS through a regular or your own audit server by entering commands, for example, sysctl, ps-aux, up to copying all OS files to check
Application program change	The application program file (node.js text) is published in advance on the website of the electoral system. The server administrator places a copy of this file in his/her /home/admin/ directory, and the voter copies it through the audit server for comparison with the published one. When the program is launched, the administrator creates a report on his/her actions using the history > [report file name] command. The voter checks the report and compares the time of its creation with the moment the program was launched (ps-aux command on the audit server). If the file was correct before launch, then there was no substitution
Extraordinary intervention of personnel	The audit server logs the appearance of all active processes, including administrator actions. After starting the program and creating a report, no one should interfere with the server. The auditor, using the «Audit Protocol» key, checks that there are no records after starting the program, which indicates that there is no outside intervention in the server

It should be noted that the admission of voters to inspect the server block and participate in the installation of the OS can be allowed during the period of time before the voting, when there is no critical data on the server. The duration of this period is approximately one month. This is enough for voters to be convinced that it is impossible to create an imitator on the existing equipment that would create the appearance of fair elections, but in reality would allow fraud. It is not required that each voter inspect the server hardware, but it is desirable that one of them exercise this right, since it is important to record the result of the ps-aux command, which is shown in Fig. 7. This command displays a summary of all active processes.

```

ps -aux
USER      PID %CPU %MEM    VSZ   RSS Tt  STAT   STARTED      TIME COMMAND
root      39820  1.8  0.4  1308  3432 ??  S       1:25PM    0:00.38 sshd: kontro
root         1  0.0  0.0   440   316 ??  S       8Jul21   9:53.69 /sbin/init
root     19788  0.0  0.1   724   532 ??  Ip      8Jul21   0:00.17 /sbin/slaacd
_slaacd   50298  0.0  0.1   724   572 ??  Ip      8Jul21   0:00.05 slaacd: engi
_slaacd   97395  0.0  0.1   728   600 ??  Ip      8Jul21   0:00.04 slaacd: fron
root     77435  0.0  0.2   812  1988 ??  IpU     8Jul21   0:00.43 syslogd: [pr
_syslogd  19541  0.0  0.1  1400  1308 ??  Sp      8Jul21  23:44.89 /usr/sbin/sy
root     89941  0.0  0.1   720   480 ??  IU      8Jul21   0:00.02 pflogd: [pri
_pflogd   1611  0.0  0.0   756   444 ??  Sp      8Jul21  23:32.26 pflogd: [run
_ntpd    42631  0.0  0.3  1144  2392 ??  I<p    8Jul21   1:33.14 ntpd: ntp en
_ntpd    50686  0.0  0.2  1060  2256 ??  Ip      8Jul21   0:00.46 ntpd: dns en
root     23582  0.0  0.1  1028  1328 ??  I<pU    8Jul21   0:01.11 /usr/sbin/nt
root     39753  0.0  0.1  1232  1320 ??  S       8Jul21 103:18.57 /usr/sbin/ss
root     42239  0.0  0.2  2000  1996 ??  Ip      8Jul21   0:02.26 /usr/sbin/sm
_smtpd   14505  0.0  0.4  1660  3432 ??  Ip      8Jul21   0:00.20 smtprd: klond
_smtpd   93816  0.0  0.4  1940  3736 ??  Ip      8Jul21   0:00.99 smtprd: contr
_smtpd   29763  0.0  0.4  1772  3676 ??  Ip      8Jul21   0:01.42 smtprd: looku
_smtpd   77896  0.0  0.4  2044  4128 ??  Ip      8Jul21   0:02.81 smtprd: pony
_smtpd   40229  0.0  0.4  1952  3728 ??  Ip      8Jul21   0:02.90 smtprd: queue
_smtpd   21890  0.0  0.4  1672  3532 ??  Ip      8Jul21   0:00.48 smtprd: sched
_sndiop   87793  0.0  0.1   560   784 ??  IpU     8Jul21   0:00.00 sndiod: help
_sndio   40541  0.0  0.1   588   684 ??  I<p    8Jul21   0:00.01 /usr/bin/snd
root     93843  0.0  0.1   736  1140 ??  Ip      8Jul21   1:50.46 /usr/sbin/cr
kontrol   9930  0.1  0.3  1232  2636 ??  S       1:25PM    0:00.03 sshd: kontro
admin    62604  0.0  5.6 220220 52632 p0-  S      14Jul21  44:38.87 node --exper
kontrol   85491  0.0  0.1   800   660 p0  Sp      1:25PM    0:00.03 -ksh (ksh)
kontrol   4955  0.0  0.0   472   344 p0  R+pU/2  1:25PM    0:00.00 ps -aux
root     63197  0.0  0.1   464  1080 00  I+pU    8Jul21   0:00.04 /usr/libexec
b66$ exit

```

Fig. 7. The result of running the ps-aux command in the audit server window

If the PID values (second column in **Fig. 7**) for active operating system processes remain unchanged, this means that the server has been running continuously since the time indicated in the STARTED column. In this case, from July 8, 2021. Because every time starting OpenBSD, all but the first process generates random PIDs, it is not possible to restart the server with the same PIDs. The audit server continuously monitors active processes by issuing the ps-aux command every few seconds and raises an alarm if a new process appears.

Thus, in the described voting system, voters can conduct a full-fledged audit and make sure that their vote cannot be disclosed by an attacker when transmitted over communication channels and that there was no outside interference in the operation of the voting server.

3. 3. Methodology for a full-fledged audit of the Internet voting system

According to this methodology, the audit is presented in the form of two stages: preparatory and remote. It is assumed that among the voters there are those who, independently or with the involvement of proxies, will take part in the preparatory stage of the audit on the territory of the ISP (Internet Service Provider). The number of such voters need not be limited. The task of the preparatory stage is to check the hardware of the vote recording server and its operating system for compliance with the nomenclature of the hardware, as well as to check the operability of the remote audit. First of all, it is necessary to make sure that the server is really running on a Raspberry Pi 3 Model B mini-computer. This can be checked by appearance, as well as using the sysctl hw command, the result of which is shown in **Fig. 8**, where the computer type is listed as hw.product.

```
sysctl hw

hw.machine=arm64
hw.model=ARM Cortex-A53 r0p4
hw.ncpu=4
hw.byteorder=1234
hw.pagesize=4096
hw.disknames=sd0:89481f1157690de7
hw.diskcount=1
hw.sensors.bcmtemp0.temp0=32.71 degC
hw.product=Raspberry Pi 3 Model B Rev 1.2
hw.physmem=959225856
hw.usermem=959213568
hw.ncpufound=4
hw.allowpowerdown=1
hw.ncpuonline=4
b66$ exit
```

Fig. 8. The result of executing the sysctl hw command

The version of the operating system can be found using the uname – a command. To execute commands, it is necessary to connect a console, which can be any computer with a USB port. **Fig. 9** shows connecting the console to a Raspberry Pi 3 Model B.

Fig. 9. Connecting the console to a Raspberry Pi 3 mini computer

The power cord is shown on the left, and the cable to the Ethernet switch is shown below. These and only these two cords must be connected at all times. The cable for connecting the

console via a UART-USB type adapter is shown on the right. Checking the Internet connection is carried out by the `ifconfig` command, the result of which is shown in **Fig. 10**.

```
ifconfig

lo0: flags=8049<UP,LOOPBACK,RUNNING,MULTICAST> mtu 32768
    index 2 priority 0 llprio 3
    groups: lo
    inet6 ::1 prefixlen 128
    inet6 fe80::1%lo0 prefixlen 64 scopeid 0x2
    inet 127.0.0.1 netmask 0xff000000

enc0: flags=0<>
    index 1 priority 0 llprio 3
    groups: enc
    status: active

smac0: flags=8843<UP,BROADCAST,RUNNING,SIMPLEX,MULTICAST> mtu 1500
    lladdr b8:27:eb:b8:5f:ca
    index 3 priority 0 llprio 3
    groups: egress
    media: Ethernet autoselect (100baseTX full-duplex)
    status: active
    inet 91.198.50.130 netmask 0xfffff00 broadcast 91.198.50.255

pflog0: flags=141<UP,RUNNING,PROMISC> mtu 33136
    index 4 priority 0 llprio 3
    groups: pflog
```

Fig. 10. The result of running the `ifconfig` command

This command shows the status of the interfaces in use, three of which are service (`lo0`, `enc0`, `pflog0`) and one (`smac0`) for connecting to the Internet. No other interfaces with the active status should be discovered. If there is any doubt about the integrity of the operating system, then it is necessary to copy all its files for additional verification, which is described in detail in [15]. This check consists in loading exactly the same OS using exactly the same method on your computer, and then comparing the files. If the result of the comparison is positive, there is no doubt about the integrity of the system, since it is impossible to modify the system, keeping all its executable files unchanged. After making sure that the OS is correct, it is possible to enter the `ps -aux` command through the console, the result of which was shown above (**Fig. 7**). All results of command execution must be stored in memory for later comparison. Next, it is necessary to check the performance of remote audit. To do this, using any Internet access device using the link published by the provider it is necessary to open the voter's Web page. By pressing the audit key, let's open the page of the audit server, the view of which is shown above (**Fig. 3**). By pressing the OS command enter key, let's enter the same commands that were entered through the console, and check the results. For the `ifconfig` command, the results must match completely, for the `sysctl hw` command, only the processor temperature value may differ, and for the `ps -aux` command, the PID values of all active OS processes must match. These results should be published on the voters' website. In case of distrust of the standard audit server, the provider must assist voters to install an additional audit server. The principle of operation of the audit server is described in detail in [10]. For voters to access the audit server, the https protocol is recommended in order to neutralize the attack of an intermediary. At the end of the preparatory stage of the audit, it is possible to check the receipt of requests from voters to the voting server based on the records in the `/home/admin/nohup.out` file. To do this, after the voter's request to the voting server, enter the `cat /home/admin/nohup.out` command through the console and check the address that will be displayed at the end of the file in the form: `ADDR = 217.66.97.56:63173`. This address must match the real IP address of the voter request. The subsequent audit can be performed remotely. To do this, on the Web page of the voter, press the audit key, which leads to the opening of the main Web page of the audit server. Next, by pressing the «OS Command» key, it is necessary to execute commands for comparison, the results of which are published on the voters' website. In addition, voters can check the contents of all application software files, which makes it possible to compare the texts of executed programs with published ones, as well as check the commands entered by the administrator against the report files. Although these checks make it possible to make sure that there was no tampering with the hardware and software of the voting server, they are not enough to be completely convincing in the absence of falsifications. The most important two checks

that need to be performed at a certain time concern the detection of man-in-the-middle attacks and tampering with the voting server. The first of these checks must be performed by the voter during a dialogue with the voting server, since a man-in-the-middle attack can be implemented at any time. A detailed description of this check is given above (Fig. 4, 5). The second of these checks must be performed after the results of the vote have been received. It consists in viewing the audit protocol using the «Audit Protocol» button (Fig. 3). The results of pressing this key are shown in Fig. 11, 12.

```
Server Start 14.07.2021 19:18:48
Start Control 11.02.2022 18:10:18
```

Fig. 11. Audit protocol when there is no interference with the operation of the server

```
Server Start 14.07.2021 19:18:48
Start Control 11.02.2022 16:32:09
admin 62604 11.02.2022 16:32:29 !!!!!!!!!!!!
admin 62604 0.0 5.6 220220 52428 p0- S
admin 74413 11.02.2022 16:32:29 !!!!!!!!!!!!
admin 74413 0.0 0.1 800 664 p0 I+p

admin 62604 11.02.2022 16:32:59 !!!!!!!!!!!!
admin 62604 0.0 5.6 220220 52428 p0- S
admin 74413 11.02.2022 16:32:59 !!!!!!!!!!!!
admin 74413 0.0 0.1 800 664 p0 I+p

admin 62604 11.02.2022 16:33:29 !!!!!!!!!!!!
admin 62604 0.0 5.6 220220 52432 p0- S
admin 74413 11.02.2022 16:33:29 !!!!!!!!!!!!
admin 74413 0.0 0.1 800 664 p0 I+p

admin 62604 11.02.2022 16:33:59 !!!!!!!!!!!!
admin 62604 0.0 5.6 220220 52436 p0- S
admin 74413 11.02.2022 16:33:59 !!!!!!!!!!!!
admin 74413 0.0 0.1 800 664 p0 I+p

admin 62604 11.02.2022 16:34:29 !!!!!!!!!!!!
admin 62604 0.0 5.6 220220 52436 p0- S
admin 74413 11.02.2022 16:34:29 !!!!!!!!!!!!
admin 74413 0.0 0.1 800 664 p0 I+p

Stop Control 11.02.2022 16:34:32
Start Control 11.02.2022 16:53:08
```

Fig. 12. Type of audit protocol in case of interference with the server at the preparatory stage of the audit

When checking the audit protocol, it is important to pay attention to the start time of the last control, after which there should be no records. If to turn on control at the preparatory stage of the audit, then unnecessary entries will fall into the protocol (Fig. 12). This can be useful for checking the functionality of the automatic audit system. Thus, by performing an audit according to the presented methodology, all threats that cause concern on the part of voters can be identified. During the preparatory stage of the audit, it is confirmed that the voting server is actually implemented on a Raspberry Pi 3 Model B mini-computer running OpenBSD. At the same time, it is impossible to covertly replace these tools, since any attempt to log on to the server with administrator rights is immediately logged by the audit server. Thanks to the preparatory stage of the audit in the conditions of an open server block, voters can continue a full-fledged audit remotely until the complete completion of the voting server. Thanks to the remote audit stage, voters can be sure that the application software has not been tampered with and that there has been no outside interference with the server. This indicates that the results of the vote count published on the server could not be falsified.

3. 4. Simulation of the system of secret Internet voting

The purpose of this simulation was to confirm the possibility of practical implementation of a full-fledged audit according to the developed methodology and to determine the qualitative characteristics of such a voting system.

First of all, let's note that the modeling concerned only that part of the system that required an audit to ensure the secrecy of the expression of will and the absence of fraud in determining the result. The underlying principles of this simulation in terms of hardware selection were that the products be mass-produced, widely available, highly reliable, and easily identifiable by appearance. In addition, they should be inexpensive, so that if there is doubt about the authenticity, there are no problems with replacing them. In terms of software, the main requirement was its complete openness and the ability to verify the absence of malicious bookmarks. For tools that are used in finished form, the main thing is their safety, and for the created application software, the maximum availability and popularity of language tools. A special requirement was the choice of the most simple and understandable software solutions, as well as minimizing the volume of programs to facilitate their detailed verification. All these requirements were taken into account when choosing the principles for constructing this voting system, which was described above. In the model of an open block of servers, shown in **Fig. 13**, it is provided to connect a console to them for control by auditors.

Fig. 13. The work of the auditor through the console with an open block of servers

An important part of the simulation was the preparation of such voters who could not only vote, but also audit the software. Since the modeling was carried out among students who already mastered computer languages at school, working with this model contributed to their creative development. The most difficult part of the model to understand was cryptographic transformations, which are based on calculating the degree of large numbers according to the rules of operations on the Galois field $GF(2^{503})$. To simplify auditing, this calculation is implemented as a block placed in the CRIPTO.js file, containing no more than 100 JavaScript statements. This block has been repeatedly tested and does not need to be checked. The actions programmed in this block are performed on character strings of zeros and ones of 503 characters each. Cryptographic transformations on the client and server sides are symmetrical and are performed by identical JavaScript programs. The implementation of the Diffie-Hellman algorithm looks like this:

$$C_C(C_S(q, X), Y) = C_S(C_C(q, Y), X), \quad (1)$$

where C_C and C_S are the transformations performed by the CRIPTO.js block on the client and server sides, respectively; q – character string 010000, representing a primitive element of the Galois field; X and Y are strings of random characters (0, 1) generated on the server and client side, respectively.

Since the transformations C_C and C_S are the same, and expression (1) in arithmetic equivalent has the form:

$$(q^X)^Y = (q^Y)^X, \quad (2)$$

then the validity of equality (1) is beyond doubt. This means that on the server and client sides, the same sequences of 503 random characters 0 and 1 are obtained. The data for encryption is converted into character strings 0 and 1, and then the next character from the random sequence is added modulo 2 to each character. For decryption on the recipient side, exactly the same transformation is performed, since the Vernam cipher is symmetrical.

Thus, the simulation showed that the audit of the system, including the most difficult to understand part of the software, is available to students with only a school education. It is for this generation that new voting systems are being created, in which, thanks to a widely available full-fledged audit, unreasonable suspicions of possible fraud are eliminated.

4. Discussion of the results

With the traditional voting technology, as indicated in [1], due to a full-fledged audit, voters do not have suspicions of fraud. However, with the same technological capabilities in other countries, elections can end in scandals. This indicates that if the need for honest voting has not matured in society, then conditions for a full-fledged audit will not be created or its results will be ignored. This paper shows that with Internet voting, thanks to the open block of servers, it becomes possible to conduct a full-fledged audit. To do this, it is enough that voters follow the methodology presented in this article, but this does not mean that the results of the audit cannot be ignored. In other words, the article proves that the introduction of Internet voting can be done without losing the opportunity in a full-fledged audit, which before the appearance of this work there could be doubts.

It should be noted that in order to conduct a full-fledged audit, it is required that some of the voters have knowledge of the basics of Internet technologies. This means that in the near future such technologies can be successfully applied, since today's schoolchildren already have such knowledge.

5. Conclusions

Based on the fact that the fears of voters are related only to the disclosure of the secrecy of their vote and the possible falsification of the vote count, the blocks and procedures in the Internet voting system that can cause distrust of voters are determined.

The principles of building a secret Internet voting system based on the use of an open server block are chosen, which ensures the possibility of conducting a full-fledged audit not only by the voters themselves, but also by any of their proxies.

A methodology for conducting a full-fledged audit of the Internet voting system on the Internet has been developed. Thanks to this technique, such an audit does not require the involvement of high-level specialists, but it is quite enough to receive a modern school education.

A model of the secret Internet voting system has been created, including the means of conducting an audit according to the developed methodology. Thanks to this model, it is shown that there are no problems with the choice of hardware and software for the implementation of a full-fledged audit in secret Internet voting systems. For experimental voting, the model is available on the Internet at <http://91.198.50.130:29900/VD999900.html>.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest in relation to this research, whether financial, personal, authorship or otherwise, that could affect the research and its results presented in this paper.

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Data availability

Manuscript has no associated data.

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